

1 **Hagl, a HOXD antisense growth-associated long non-coding RNA with functions in lineage**
2 **commitment in the human embryo.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of the
9 ncRNA *HAGLR* as a lineage commitment factor or lineage commitment cooperating factor in embryonic
10 stem cells of the human embryo.

11 Citations

12 1. Zakany, J., Darbellay, F., Mascrez, B., Necsulea, A. and Duboule, D., 2017. Control of growth and
13 gut maturation by HoxD genes and the associated lncRNA Hagl. Proceedings of the National Academy of
14 Sciences, 114(44), pp.E9290-E9299.